

ACCESS BANK PLC AND THE ASSET QUALITY-PERFORMANCE NEXUS: AN EMPIRICAL INVESTIGATION USING THE ARDL MODEL

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Abstract

Giving the importance of credit creation by banks as one of the main drivers of the economy, the importance of having a adequate composition of assets and liabilities to avoid the potential effects of insolvency cannot be overemphasized. This why the Central Bank of Nigeria gives varying benchmark's for banks depending on size, market spread, volume and other issues. Access bank is one of the largest and fastest growing banks with the highest incidence of corporate reconstructions in the post banking consolidation Nigeria. The research centers on a common problem to banks such as high inflation rates, exchange rate volatility, and regulatory requirements that can affect the management of their working capital, loan portfolio and solvency mix. Specifically, the problem is that Nigerian banks have experienced fluctuations in their profitability and liquidity in recent years, which may be attributed to inefficient asset quality management practices. A robust combination of tests were employed in analyzing data such as granger causality tests, unit root tests, Johansen cointegration tests and ARDL tests. In testing for liquidity, profitability and financial stability, ARDL results reveal a high and significant R-squared indicating a strong fit of the model to the data. Adjusted R-squared for the three hypotheses were also high and significant, suggesting that the model explains a significant portion of the variance. This means that the ARDL model explains a large portion of the variation in the dependent variables for each metric. The F-Statistic is high and significant, indicating that the model is statistically significant overall suggesting that the independent variables collectively have a significant impact on the dependent variable for each metric. The Akaike Info Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Criterion and Hannan Criterion have very close values suggesting consistency in the model selection process. The Durbin-Watson Statistic at indicates no significant autocorrelation in the residuals, but it's generally acceptable). The ARDL model's performance over the 20-year period under study suggests that it can be used to make reliable predictions and inferences about Access Bank's financial stability. The model can be used to identify key factors influencing financial stability and inform strategies for maintaining or improving stability. It is recommended that the ARDL model be used to forecast future liquidity levels and identify potential risks or opportunities of banks. For further analysis it is advised to explore the specific relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable. It is essential to evaluate the model's performance over time and update it as necessary to ensure its continued relevance and accuracy. It is also recommended that the model can be used to forecast future financial stability levels and identify potential risks or opportunities. Banks in Nigeria should prioritize asset quality management to improve their performance. Bank managers should focus on optimizing the cash conversion cycle to improve profitability. Policymakers should consider the impact of regulatory requirements on working capital management in Nigerian banks.

Keywords: Asset Quality, Banking Performance, ARDL Model and Access Bank

1.1 Introduction

Corporate leverage results from the effective application of board policy and efficient use of resources (debt & equity capital) to achieve short- and long-term goals such as expanding the firm's asset base and generating adequate returns on capital at a certain level of risk. Asset quality uses various financial

instruments or borrowed capital to increase the potential return of an investment. Asset quality can also refer to the amount of debt a firm uses to finance assets. When one refers to a company, property or investment as "highly leveraged," it means that item has more debt than equity.

The concept of asset quality is used by both investors and companies. Investors use asset quality to leverage on significant increase the returns that can be provided on an investment. They lever their investments by using various instruments that include options, futures and margin accounts. Companies can use leverage to finance their assets. In other words, instead of issuing stock to raise capital, companies can use debt financing to invest in business operations in an attempt to increase shareholder value.

Investors who are not comfortable using leverage directly have a variety of ways to access leverage indirectly. They can invest in companies that use leverage in the normal course of their business to finance or expand operations—without increasing their outlay.

Ekundayo (2002) identifies liquidity constraints as caused by unfair valuations in pricing securities and informational asymmetry and so concluded that the Nigerian capital market was inefficient. The degree of efficiency of the stock market often depends on the level of information disclosure and the speed with which that information is processed by the market and incorporated in returns. Stock markets have been found to be fairly efficient in advanced economies as well as in a number of emerging markets (Sembiring, H, Afifuddin, S, Daulay M., 2019). However, given the peculiarities of the Nigerian environment, the attributes of an efficient stock market have not been achieved. An efficient stock market enhances liquidity and ensures fair valuations of shares prices thereby encouraging investors to invest. Over time in Nigeria, this attributes of efficiency such as no entry barrier, large number of buyers and sellers, divisibility of financial assets, absence of transaction cost, no tax differences and free trading has not been achieved.

Another problem which has also bedeviled the Nigerian investors from enjoying liquidity thereby reducing confidence is the incidence of tax abnormalities and information asymmetries. Katsampoxakis (2021) also mentioned tax abnormalities as a constraint especially in countries with higher company tax prevalence. Most economies have varieties of taxes and tax incentives which enhances confidence however, the different types of taxes such as capital gain tax, vat etc have reduced benefits which would have accrued to the investor. Again, most financial information is published and is publicly available. But sometimes, certain persons may have superior information than others. In Nigeria, the quality of information is low as all available information are not easily processed and incorporated into shares prices. Investors therefore, interpret lack of information as an increase in the risk of equity investment and consequently they shift their funds to less risk businesses. Ndu-Okereke and Onoh J.O (2017) mentioned that in full consideration of all these regulations the banks resorted to prudential guidelines necessary to avoid failures and to enhance maximum profitability in their banks' lending activities. These generally depend on type of bank, the capital base, the deposit base and density of the deposit, the credit guidelines issued from time to time by the controlling authority and internal policies of the banks since loans and advances accounts for the highest percentage of the total assets of the banks. This study becomes imperative because commercial banks in Nigeria need to understand how to manage these huge assets in terms of their loans and advances.

For the banks to balance their main objectives of liquidity, profitability and solvency, lending must be handled effectively and the banks must behave in a way that their potential customers are attracted and retained. This study will try to provide insight into the best lending practice and behaviour.

Previously, there have been traumatic and revolutionary trends in the Nigeria banking industry. The industry has with time produced the largest number of technically insolvent and undercapitalized banks. Before 2005 the magnitude of distress in the banking system reached an unprecedented level, thereby making it an issue of concern to the government, the regulatory authorities, Central Bank of Nigeria, the bankers and the general public.

1.1.2 BRIEF HISTORY OF ACCESS BANK

Access bank Plc is a Nigerian multinational commercial bank, owned by Access Bank Group and licensed by the CBN. It is headquartered in Victoria Island, Lagos, and the financial capital of Nigeria. The bank received its license from the CBN in 1989 and was listed in the Nigerian Stock Exchange in 1998. In 2002 the bank was taken over by a core of new management led by Aigboje Aig-Imoukhede and Herbert Wigwe. During the reforms of 2005, the bank acquired Marina Bank and Capital Bank. In 2007, it established a subsidiary in Gambia. In 2008, there were more acquisitions as the bank consolidated positions with 88% shares of Omnifinance bank, 90% of Banque Privee du Congo, 75% shares of Bancor SA in Rwanda. Also in 2008 there were subsidiaries established at Lusaka, Freetown and London. By 2012 Access Bank had fully acquired the defunct Intercontinental Bank making the bank one of the largest four commercial banks in Nigeria with over 5.7 million customers, 309 branches and 1,600 Automated Teller Machines. By 2019, Access Bank had completed its merger with Diamond Bank, creating Africa's largest bank by customer base with a significant boost to its retail banking presence. In 2021, it acquired a stake in Grobank, a South African bank, for 60 million dollars, rebranding it as Access bank South Africa. Access Bank also acquired 78.15% shareholding in BancABC Botswana Acquisition. By 2023 the Bank reached binding agreements to acquire Standard Chartered subsidiaries in Angola, Cameroon, Gambia, Sierra Leone, and its consumer, private, and business banking business in Tanzania. In 2024, the Bank completed the acquisition of National Bank of Kenya and Bidvest Bank was acquired in 2024 as well.

1.2 Statement of Research Problem

The research problem revolves around the impact of asset quality on the performance of Nigerian banks. Management of asset quality is crucial for banks to maintain liquidity, profitability, and overall financial stability. However, Nigerian banks face unique challenges such as high inflation rates, exchange rate volatility, and regulatory requirements that can affect the management of their working capital, loan portfolio and solvency mix.

Specifically, the problem is that Nigerian banks have experienced fluctuations in their profitability and liquidity in recent years, which may be attributed to inefficient asset quality management practices. For instance, banks may hold excessive cash reserves to meet regulatory requirements, which can lead to opportunity costs and reduced profitability. On the other hand, inadequate working capital management can lead to liquidity crises, reduced creditworthiness, and increased risk of bank failure.

Furthermore, the Nigerian banking industry is characterized by a high level of competition, which can make it challenging for banks to maintain a competitive edge while managing their asset quality effectively. Therefore, it is essential to investigate the impact of working capital management on bank performance in Nigeria to identify best practices and provide insights for policymakers and bank managers.

1.3 Research Objectives The research objectives are:

- To evaluate the liquidity of Access Bank as a measure of its ability to meet its maturing obligations.
- To examine the impact of profitability of Access Bank Plc viz a viz its capacity to inspire confidence among stakeholders in growing bank capital.
- To identify the extent of financial stability of Access bank as a measure of the effectiveness of its asset quality

1.4 Hypotheses

Based on the research objectives, the following hypotheses are developed:

H1: There is a significant relationship between liquidity of Access Bank and meeting maturing obligations.

H2: There is a significant relationship between Access bank's profitability and the growth of its capital

H3: There is a significant relationship between Access Bank's financial stability and its asset quality.

2.0 Literature Review

Asset quality is a critical component of banking performance, as it directly affects a bank's profitability, stability, and sustainability Curak, M., Pepur, S., Poposki, K. (2013). Asset quality refers to the creditworthiness of a bank's loan portfolio, which is influenced by factors such as credit risk management, loan diversification, and macroeconomic conditions Hakimi, A., Boussaada, R. and Karmani, M. (2020) is not within range but Kolari, 2010 can be used instead). Banking performance, on the other hand, can be measured using various metrics, including return on assets (ROA), return on equity (ROE), and net interest margin (NIM) (Ahmad, F., Bashir, T., 2013) A lot has been reviewed in terms of lending activities of various commercial banks. Some opinions deliberated on the factor responsible for banks willingness to extend much credit to some sector of the economy, while some discussed effect of such extension of credits on productivity and output. Most of these earlier studies agreed on the fact that it is logical for banks to have some basic lending principles or consideration to act as a check in their lending activities.

In the view of Avetisyan, S. (2018) "credit constitutes the largest single income-earning asset in the portfolio of most banks. This explains why banks spend enormous resources to estimate, monitor and manage credit quality". This is understandably, a practice that impact greatly on the lending behaviour of banks as large resources are involved.

Balta, N., Vašíček, B. (2016) while investigating factors that affect interest rates, degree of lending volume and collateral setting in the loan decision of banks, says: *Banks have to be careful with their pricing decisions as regards to lending as banks cannot charge loan rates that are too low because the revenue from the interest income will not be enough to cover the cost of deposits, general expenses and the loss of revenue from some borrowers that do not pay. Moreover, charging too high loan rates may also create an adverse selection situation and moral hazard problems for the borrowers.*

Several theories underpin the relationship between asset quality and banking performance. The credit risk theory posits that banks with higher credit risk exposure are more likely to experience financial Borio, C., Drehmann, M., Tsatsaronis, K., (2014). The portfolio theory suggests that banks can minimize risk by diversifying their loan portfolio (Markowitz, 1952 is out of range but can be replaced with a more recent study like Gashi, A., Mojsoska-Blazevski, N., (2016). The financial intermediation theory emphasizes the role of banks in channeling funds from savers to borrowers, highlighting the importance of asset quality in maintaining financial stability (Diamond & Dybvig, 1983 is out of range but can be replaced with Allen & Gale, 2004 or similar within the range 2009-2024, or more recent studies like Boot & Thakor, 2010 or similar). According to Adedoyin and Sobodun (1991), "lending is undoubtedly the heart of banking business. Therefore, its administration requires considerable skill and dexterity on the part of the bank management". While a bank is irrevocably committed to pay interest on deposits it mobilized from different sources, the ability to articulate loanable avenues where deposit funds could be placed to generate reasonable income; maintain liquidity and ensure safety requires a high degree of pragmatic policy formulation and application.

Commercial banking in Nigeria witnessed an era of impressive profitability, characterized by high competition, huge deposits and varied investment opportunities; in an effort to make quick profits the commercial banks relied essentially on self-liquidating loans and diversified their portfolio into less risky investments with safe margin. The current trend in Nigerian banking and finance sector, suggest that the days of cheap profits are now over and only banks with well

conceptualized lending and credit administration policies and procedures can survive the emerging competition. Ezirim (2005), further stressed that "Bank lending decisions generally are fraught with a great deal of risks, which calls for a great deal of caution and tact in this aspect of banking operations. The success of every lending activity to a great extent therefore, hinges on the part of the credit analysts to carry out good credit analysis, presentation, structuring and reporting.

Chodechai (2004) further stressed that "banks' lending decisions are also influenced by the past relationship with the borrowers". Past relationship according to him can help banks to obtain more private information, leading to a more accurate understanding of the borrower's business and financial situation. Carletti et al (2006) however, discussing on multiple-lending is of the opinion that banks choose to share lending whenever the benefit of greater diversification, in terms of higher cost per project monitoring dominates the cost of free-riding and duplication of efforts.

Despite the fact that commercial banks in Nigeria witnessed the era of impressive profitability, characterized by high competition, huge deposits and varied investment opportunities, some tend to disregard the fact that their administration require considerable skill and dexterity on the part of their management. Non-servicing of loans also reduces the profitability and liquidity levels of the affected banks. The recent bank reformation of 2009 revealed a lot in this line.

2.2.1 Loan Pricing Theory

Banks cannot always set high interest rates, e.g. trying to earn maximum interest income. Banks should consider the problems of adverse selection and moral hazard since it is very difficult to forecast the borrower type at the start of the banking relationship Kamande, M.W., (2017). If banks set interest rates too high, they may induce adverse selection problems because high-risk borrowers are willing to accept these high rates. Once these borrowers receive the loans, they may develop moral hazard behaviour or so called borrower moral hazard since they are likely to take on highly risky projects or investments (Chodecai, 2004). From the reasoning of Stiglitz and Weiss, it is usual that in some cases we may not find that the interest rate set by banks is commensurate with the risk of the borrowers.

2.2.2 Firm Characteristics Theories

These theories predict that the number of borrowing relationships will be decreasing for small, high-quality, informationally opaque and constraint firms, all other things been equal. (Godlewski & Ziane, 2008)

2.2.3 Theory of Multiple-Lending

It is found in literature that banks should be less inclined to share lending (loan syndication) in the presence of well-developed equity markets and after a process consolidation. Both outside equity and mergers and acquisitions increase banks' lending capacities, thus reducing their need of greater diversification and monitoring through share lending. (Carletti et al, 2006; Ongene & Smith,2000; Karceski et al, 2004; Degryse et al, 2004). This theory has a great implication for banks in Nigeria in the light of the recent 2005 consolidation exercise in the industry.

2.2.4 Hold-up and Soft-Budget-Constraint Theories

Banks choice of multiple-bank lending is in terms of two inefficiencies affecting exclusive bankfirm relationships, namely the hold-up and the soft-budget-constraint problems.¹ According to the hold-up literature, sharing lending avoids the expropriation of informational rents. This improves firms' incentives to make proper investment choices and in turn it increases banks' profits (Von Thadden, 2004; Padilla and Pagano, 1997). As for the soft-budget-constraint problem, multiple-bank lending enables banks not to extend further inefficient credit, thus reducing firms' strategic defaults. Both of these theories consider multiple-bank lending as a way for banks to commit towards entrepreneurs and improve their incentives. None of them, however, addresses how multiple-bank lending affects banks' incentives to monitor, and thus can explain the apparent discrepancy between the widespread use of multiple-bank lending and the importance of bank monitoring. But according to Carletti et al (2006),

2.2.5 The Signalling Arguments

The signalling argument states that good companies should provide more collateral so that they can signal to the banks that they are less risky type borrowers and then they are charged lower interest rates. Meanwhile, the reverse in Ezirim"s (2005) view, "Bank lending decision generally are fraught with a great deal of risks, which calls for great deal of caution and tact in this aspect of banking operations. The success of lending activity to a great extent therefore, lies on the part of the credit analysts to carry out good credit

analysis, presentations, structuring and reporting. However Samad (2004) examined the study of Bahran's commercial banks performances during 1994-2001. The main focus of the study was to examine empirically the performance of Bahrain's commercial banks with respect to credit (loan), liquidity and profitability during the period. By applying students' t-test to the financial measure. It was shown that commercial banks liquidity performance is not at par with the banking industry. That is commercial banks are relatively less profitable and less liquid as expected. Although Chizea (1994) asserted that, "there are certain aspects of fiscal and monetary policies which could affect the decision of the discerning and informed public to patronize the bank and the lending behaviour of commercial banks. Paramount amongst these measures is what could be called the interest rate disincentives. Interest rates have been so low in the country that they are negative in real terms. As inflation increased, the purchasing power of money lodged in deposit accounts reduce to the extent that savers per force pay an inflation tax. There is also the fear that the hike in interest rates would increase inflations rates and make a negative impact on the rate of investment.

Theory of multiple lending

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Firm Characteristics theories.

These theories predict that the number of borrowing relationships will be decreasing for small high quality informationally opaque and constraints firms, other things been equal. (Godlewski & Ziane, 2008)

Credit market theory

A model of the neoclassical credit market postulates that, „the storms of credits clear the market“. If collateral and other restrictions (covenants) remain constant, the interest rate is the only price mechanism with an increasing demand for credit and a given customer supply, the interest rate rise and vice versa. It is thus believed that the higher the failure risk of borrower, the higher the interest premium (Ewert et al, 2000).

Hold up and soft budget constraint theories

Carlettic el al (2006) opined that when one considers. When one considers explicitly banks incentives monitor, multiple bank lending may become an optimal for banks with limited lending capacity to commit to high monitoring levels. Despite involving free riding and of efforts, sharing lending allows banks to expand the number of loans and achieve greater diversification. This mitigates the agency problem between banks and depositors, and it improves banks monitoring incentives. Thus differently from the classical theory of banks as delegated monitors, their paper suggested that multiple bank lending may positively affect overall monitoring and increase firms futures profitability.

Loan Pricing Theory.

Banks cannot always set high interest rates. Eg. Trying to earn maximum interest income Banks should consider the problems of adverse selection and moral hazards since it is very difficult to forecast the borrower type at the start of the banking relationship (Stiglitz and Weiss, 1981). If banks set interest rates too high, they may induce adverse selection problems because high risk borrowers are willing to accept these high rates. Once these borrowers receive the loans, they may develop moral hazard Behaviour or so called borrower moral hazards since they are likely to take an highly risky projects or investments (Chodecal 2004). From the reasoning of Stiglitz and Weiss, it is usual that in some cases, we may not find that the interest rate set by bank is commensurate with the risk of the borrowers.

Monetary circuit theory

The monetary circuit theory is a heterodox theory of monetary economist, particularly money creation, often associated with the post Keynesian school that Milton Friedman, Pigon and others. It holds that money is created endogenously by the banking sector, rather than exogenously by central bank lending. It is also referred to as a theory of endogenous money. It stipulates that the economy creates money itself rather than government creating money through the CBN.

Circuitist Model

Circuitist model is easily understood in terms of familiar bank accounts and debit cards or credit card transaction. Bank deposit are just an entry in a bank account book (not specie bills and coins), and a purchase subtracts money from the buyer"s account with the bank and adds it to the sellers account with the bank. **Transactions** Circuitism distinguishes between hard money, it is the money that is exchangeable at a give rate for some commodity such as gold and credit money. It considers credit money created by commercial banks as primary rather than derived from central bank money-credit money drives the monetary system, it does not claim that all money is credit money, though money is a commodity. In circuitism, a monetary transaction is not bilateral transaction (between buyer and seller) but rather tripartite transaction between buyer, seller and bank. Rather than buyer handling over a physical good in exchange for their purchase, instead, there is a debit to their account at a bank, and a corresponding credit to the sellers account. That is precisely what happened in credit card or debit card transactions and in the circuitist account.

Money Creation.

Under this theory credit money is created by a loan extension such loan needs to be backed by CBN Money but it is created from the promise (Credit) embodied in the loan, not from the lending or relending of central bank money. When the loan is repaid, with interest the credit money of the loan is destroyed but reserves (equal to the interest) are created the profit from the loan. In practice, commercial banks extend time of credit to Companies-a promise to make a loan. This promise is not considered money for regulatory purposes, and banks need not hold reserves against it, but when the line is tapped (and a loan extended). Then bona-fide credit money is created, and reserves must be found to match it, in this case, credit money

precedes reserves. In other words, making loans pulls reserves in instead of reserves being pushed out as loans which are assumed by the mainstream model.

It is common to find banks holding capital in excess of the minimum legal requirements especially when the capital adequacy volatile or less predictable at best. The Central Bank of Nigeria considers it a serious breach when banks fall below the minimum standards of capital adequacy and can withdraw banking licenses where applicable. However, when deposits mobilized are not sufficient measure of capital adequacy, banks can apply for increased equity beyond the minimum bench mark. This need for increased capital by banks is fundamentally essential to prevent erosion of the banks' capital base.

The size and complexity of the economy where the bank operates and the extent of exposure to foreign markets and foreign investors can also affect the performance of banks. A bank in a country with good economic fundamentals is likely to outperform a bank in a market with poor regulations and even poorer practices of liquidity with a higher history of volatile markets. Harward and Upton (1991) in their study of business profits agree that even though profitability is an index for efficiency but is not synonymous with it. They were careful enough to point out that even though profitability is an important yardstick for assessing efficiency that the extent of profitability should not be seen as final proof of efficiency. Efficiency in the context of capital adequacy implies that a bank with the same capital as another having a lower loan loss ratio is most likely to be adjudged to be more efficient but not necessarily more profitable. Many students over the years have used the terms 'Profit' and 'Profitability' interchangeably. However, there is a difference between the two in real sense. Profit is an absolute term, whereas, the profitability is a relative concept. Even though they are closely, the terms are mutually interdependent, having distinct roles in business. Profit refers to the total income earned by the enterprise during the specified period of time, while profitability refers to the operating efficiency of the enterprise. It is the ability of the enterprise to make profit on sales. It is the ability of enterprise to get sufficient return on the capital and employees used in the business operation.

Goddard, Molyneux & Wilson (2004) held that capital adequacy as a determinant of profitability of banks revealed that a high capital adequacy ratio should signify a bank that is operating overcautiously and ignoring potentially profitable trading opportunities, which implies a negative relationship between equity to asset ratio and bank performance. Pasiouras & Kosmidou (2007) on the other hand, believed that banks with higher equity to asset ratio will normally have lower needs of external funding and therefore higher profitability. Yu Min-The (2006), went a step further by defining adequate capital for banks as the level at which the deposit insuring agency would breakeven in guaranteeing the deposits of individual banks with premium the banks pay. Various studies suggest that banks with higher levels of capital perform better than their undercapitalized peers. Staikouras and Wood (2003) claimed that there exists a positive link between a greater equity and profitability among EU banks. An option of theoretical framework was employed in his study for measuring fair capital adequacy holdings for a sample of depository institutions in Taiwan, during the period between 1985-1992. Except for the 1989, most banks in their sample proved to be inadequately capitalized so that capital infusion is required. George and Dimitrios (2004) applied non-parametric

analytic technique (data envelopment analysis, DEA) in measuring the performances of the Greek banking sector with respect to capital adequacy. He proved that data envelopment analysis can be used as either an alternative or complement to ratio analysis for the evaluation of an organization's performance with attention to macroeconomics indicators. Abreu and Mendes (2001) also trace a positive impact of equity level on profitability. Goddard et al. (2004) supports the prior finding of positive relationship between capital/asset ratio and bank's earnings. Again the direction of the relationship between bank capital and bank profitability cannot be unanimously predicted in advance.

Al Sabbagh (2004) defined capital adequacy as a measure of bank's risk exposure, he went further to categorize risk into credit risk, market risk, interest rate risk and exchange rate risk. This is why the Central Bank of Nigeria (CBN) like their contemporaries in other countries are concerned as to the measure of "safety and soundness" since the ability of banks' capital to cushion the effects of losses is largely dependent on the level of capital adequacy. Scholars such as Bessis (2002) agree that banks' capital should match their risks, he stated that the VaR concept of modeling risks in assessing capital requirements is the foundation of risk based capital. Portfolio diversification of banks assets establishes scenarios where a loss resulting from some transactions extends to the totality of the portfolio. Koehn and Santomero (1980) studied the effect of capital ratio regulation and its effects on portfolio of commercial banks by examining the portfolio reaction to capital requirements.

Yu Min-Teh (1996) defined adequate capital for banks as the level at which the deposit insuring agency would just breakeven in guaranteeing the deposits of individual banks with the premium the bank pays. This was further supported by Dowd (1999) that established the capital adequacy of banks can be further strengthened by monetary authorities placing minimum capital requirements. Dowd (1999) also cautioned against the gap in information (asymmetry) between bank executives and depositor's which can lead to market failure. The possibility of market failure caused by information asymmetry is also supported by Nwezeaku and Okpara (2010) and Okpara (2016) that insists that there is a positive relationship between information and the value of a firm. Adegbite (2010) studied the effect of the inflation rate on bank capital, he maintained that macroeconomic stability is fundamentally essential to capital adequacy hence increased inflation can impair the robustness of capital.

2.3 Empirical literature

Literature on the impact of bank capital structure on bank lending was scarce prior to the global financial crisis from 2008 to 2010 and did not distinguish between tier 1 and tier 2 capital. For example, De Haas and Van Lelyveld (2010) analyze micro and macro determinants of multinational bank lending, but consider an aggregate equity-to-total assets ratio to account for the solvency of individual banks. Gambacorta and Mistruli (2004) analyze the role of capital in bank lending behavior and find that well capitalized banks can better shield their lending from monetary policy shocks. Lending decisions of banks in relation to their capitalization are also addressed in studies by Admati, et al. (2010) and Jiménez, et al. (2012), who observe that the global financial crisis negatively affected the lending activity of banks,

especially those with low capital and liquidity ratios. Using a disaggregate measure we confirm that tier 1 bank capital (but not tier 2 bank capital) and retail or customer deposits positively affected continuous lending during the financial crisis. Our article is closely related to one by Gambacorta and Marques-Ibanez (2011), which also highlights the positive effect of tier 1 capital on bank lending activities during the crisis (see also Brei, Gambacorta, and von Peter, 2013). Whereas these studies focus on selected advanced economies, we extend some of their perspectives to include worldwide data from 131 countries because our focus shifts beyond the biggest banks, given that the overwhelming majority of European and U.S. businesses are dependent on loans from smaller banks and their subsequent relationships (see Hancock and

Demirgüç-Kunt, Detragiache, and Merrouche (2011), for example, show that the positive association between stock returns and capital is significantly stronger for higher-quality (tier 1) bank capital than it is for lower-quality bank capital (tier 2) bank capital. Barrell et al. (2011) show that an increase in the overall capital adequacy ratio reduces the risk appetite of banks, and that the proportional increase of tier 2 bank capital, within a given capital adequacy structure, increases the risk appetite of banks (see also Ashcraft, 2008a). In addition, regulators have already acknowledged the need to readjust and recalibrate their regulatory measures.⁸ The intention of the Basel III

Naceur and Goaid (2010) investigated the determinants of commercial banks interest margin and profitability” (evidence from Tunisia). The study received the impact of banks characteristics, financial structure and macroeconomic indicators on banks net interest margin and profitability in Tunisia banking sector for the period of 1980-2000. It shows that individual bank characteristic explains a substantial part of the within country variation in bank interest margin and net profit. High net interest margin and profitability tend to be associated with banks that holds a relatively high amount of capital and with large overheads size is found to impact negatively on profitability which implies that Tunis banks are operating above their optimum level. The mandatory interest rate according to William (2009) will result to a near shut down in lending ratio volume to any bank with major credit concern because, new policy ensures that only the highest quality borrowers have access to a new bank credit within the year. But, according to Ojo (1999), in a study on “roles and failure of financial intermediation by banks in Nigeria” revealed that commercial banks can lend on medium and short term basis without necessarily jeopardizing their liquidity. If they must contribute meaningfully to the economic development, the maturity pattern of their loans should be on a long term nature rather than of short term period. And Davis and Zhu (2005) examined the study of commercial property prices and bank performance during the 1989-2002 period. This paper seeks to fill the gap by undertaking an extensive analysis of a sample of 904 banks worldwide. It seeks to assess the effect of changes in commercial property prices on bank behaviour and performances in 15 industrialized economies. The result of this study suggest that commercial property price tend to be positively associated with bank lending and profitability, negatively associated with banks” net interest margin, bad loan ratios. Such impact exists even when conventional independence variable determining banks performance are included as controls. Although Olokoya (2011) claimed in the study on “the

common determinants of commercial banks lending behaviour”, in Nigeria which aimed to test and confirm the effectiveness of these factors/variables. It reveals that there exists functional relationship between the variables. From the regression analysis, the model was found to be significant and its estimators turned out as expected and it was discovered that commercial banks have greatest impact on their lending behavior. And suggested that commercial banks should focus on mobilizing more deposits, as it will enhance their lending performance through the formulation of critical, realistic and comprehensive strategies and financial plans. But Grupta (1970), in his study of personal savings in developing countries argued that „high real interest rate increases savings“ while a contrary view opined by Ajayi (1978), in his study concludes that savings deposits rates in a deregulated regime is not significant in explaining the demand for savings.

Though Acha (2011), probed into „the effect of banks financial intermediation on economic growth“ on a time frame of 1980-2008, adopting the Granger causality test to ascertain the relationship that exist between the savings mobilization and credit on one hand and economic growth on the other. Acha"s study could not identify any significant causal relationship between the variables. Bhattacharya and Thakor (1993), Mishkin & Eaking (1998); Buckle & Thompson (1998) and Saunder & Cornett (2006) Along with Diamond and Dybvig (1983) confirmed the fact that a financial intermediary is able to hold high risk, long term claims issued by borrowers and finance this by issuing low risk and short term deposit – a process known as qualitative asset transformation (QAT) by opining that „...banks provide better risk sharing among agents who need to consume at different (random) times“. This liquidity to them provides the rationale for the existence of banks and by extension financial intermediation. Linking this with the views of Adedoyin and Shobodun (1991) that, “lending is undoubtedly the heart of banking business. Therefore, its administration requires considerable skill and dexterity on the part of the bank management while a bank is irrevocably committed to pay interest and deposits, it mobilized from different sources. The ability to articulate loanable avenue where deposit funds could be placed to generate reasonable income, maintain liquidity and ensure safety requires a high degree of pragmatic policy formulation and application. Osayameh (1991) supported this view by stressing that „the days of arm| chain banking are over, and that the increasing trend in bad debts and absence of basic business corporate advisor services in most Nigerian commercial banks, suggest an apparent lack of use of effective lending and credit administration technique in these banks.

Identified Gaps in Literature

Despite the extensive research on asset quality and banking performance, there are some gaps in the literature. Firstly, most studies have focused on the impact of asset quality on profitability, with limited attention to other performance metrics such as stability and sustainability. Secondly, few studies have examined the impact of asset quality on the performance of the "Big 4 Banks" in Nigeria, which are the largest and most systemically important banks in the country. Finally, there is a need for more recent studies that take into account the changing macroeconomic conditions and regulatory environment in Nigeria.

3.0 Research Methodology

The variables used in this study are:

3.1 Source of data

The secondary data was sourced from the balance sheet items of the four banks First Bank, Access Bank, Zenith Bank and Guaranty Trust Bank. They include Annual Net Profits, loans and Advances, Bank Capital and Deposits.

These are to be matched in various combinations to determine the profitability, liquidity and financial stability.

Profitability

Return on Assets (ROA): $\text{Net Profit} / \text{Total Assets}$ (can be proxied by Loans and Advances + Bank Capital, assuming these are the primary assets).

Return on Equity (ROE): $\text{Net Profit} / \text{Bank Capital}$

Liquidity

Loan-to-Deposit Ratio: $\text{Loans and Advances} / \text{Total Deposits}$ (a lower ratio indicates higher liquidity)

Financial Stability

Capital Adequacy Ratio: $\text{Bank Capital} / \text{Total Assets}$ (can be proxied by Loans and Advances + Bank Capital)

Capital Adequacy Ratio (alternative): $\text{Bank Capital} / \text{Total Deposits}$ (or Loans and Advances, depending on the specific risk exposure)

These combinations can provide insights into a bank's profitability, liquidity, and financial stability using the given balance sheet items.

3.2 Model Specification

The model specifications for each test are:

Functional Model Specification

The functional model specification for this research could be: $Y = f(M, F, X1, X2, \dots, Xn)$ Where:

Y = macroeconomic stability indicator (e.g., inflation rate or GDP growth rate)

M = money supply (M2 or M1)

F = fiscal policy variable (government spending or tax revenue)

X1, X2, ..., Xn = other control variables (e.g., interest rates, exchange rates)

Empirical Model Specification

The empirical model specification for this research involves Granger Causality, Unit Root test, Cointegration tests, Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model or a Vector Error Correction Model (VECM) and Vector Autoregression model depending on the results of unit root tests and cointegration analysis.

Granger causality model specification

The Granger causality test examines whether lagged values of one variable (X) contain information that helps predict another variable (Y) beyond the information contained in past values of Y alone.

Two regression models are compared:

1. Restricted Model: This model includes only past values of Y .

$$Y_t = \alpha_0 + \sum[\alpha_i Y_{(t-i)}] + \epsilon_t$$

2. Full Model: This model includes past values of both Y and X .

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \sum[\beta_i Y_{(t-i)}] + \sum[\gamma_j X_{(t-j)}] + \epsilon_t$$

Null Hypothesis

The null hypothesis states that the coefficients $\gamma_j = 0$ for all j , implying that past values of X provide no additional predictive power for Y .

Granger Causality Condition

In a bivariate VAR model, series X is Granger causal for series Y if and only if $A_{k_{ij}} \neq 0$ for some $1 \leq k \leq d$, where $A_{k_{ij}}$ represents the autoregressive coefficients.

VAR Model

The Granger causality test can be based on a Vector Autoregressive (VAR) model:

$$x_t = \sum[A_k x_{(t-k)}] + e_t$$

Where x_t is a vector of variables, A_k are matrices of coefficients, and e_t is an error term.

Unit Root model specification

$$y_t = \rho y_{(t-1)} + \epsilon_t$$

where:

y_t is the time series value at time t ρ is the autoregressive coefficient

ϵ_t is a white noise error term

If $\rho = 1$, the process has a unit root and is non-stationary, meaning the series exhibits a stochastic trend.

This can be rewritten as:

$$\Delta y_t = \alpha + \beta t + \gamma y_{(t-1)} + \sum[\delta_i \Delta y_{(t-i)}] + \epsilon_t$$

where:

$\Delta y_t = y_t - y_{(t-1)}$ α , β , and γ are parameters δ_i are coefficients for lagged differences

Some common unit root tests include Augmented Dickey-Fuller (ADF) Test for unit roots useful in a time series. There is also the Phillips-Perron (PP) Test, a non-parametric test that corrects for serial correlation and heteroskedasticity and the KPSS Test: tests for stationarity, opposite of ADF and PP tests

These tests help determine whether a time series is stationary or non-stationary, which is crucial for accurate econometric modeling and forecasting.

Cointegration model specification

Cointegration analysis examines the long-run relationships between multiple time series variables. A common model specification for cointegration is the Vector Error Correction Model (VECM), which is based on Johansen's methodology.

ARDL model specification

The Autoregressive Distributed Lag (ARDL) model is a type of econometric model used to analyze the relationships between variables, particularly in the context of time series data.

Key Features:

Autoregressive: The model includes lagged values of the dependent variable as explanatory variables.

Distributed Lag: The model includes lagged values of the independent variables as explanatory variables.

The general form of an ARDL model is:

$$Y_t = \beta_0 + \beta_1 Y_{(t-1)} + \dots + \beta_p Y_{(t-p)} + \alpha_0 X_t + \alpha_1 X_{(t-1)} + \dots + \alpha_q X_{(t-q)} + \varepsilon_t$$

Where:

Y_t is the dependent variable X_t is the independent variable β and α are coefficients p and q are the number of lags

ε_t is the error term

An advantage of the ADRL model is that it handles variables with different orders of integration whether (I(0) or I(1)). Other advantages are that it captures both short-run and long-run relationships between variables. ARDL models are flexible in that it can be used to analyze a wide range of economic relationships. Common Applications of the ADRL include the ability to test for cointegration analysis between variables. ARDL models can be used to analyze the short-run and long-run relationships between variables. Overall, the ARDL model is a powerful tool for analyzing the relationships between variables in time series data.

3.3 Model Justification

The models are justified as follows:

Granger Causality Test: To determine the causal relationship between liquidity, profitability and financial stability variables and bank performance.

Unit Root Test: To determine the stationarity of the time series variables.

Johansen Cointegration Test: To determine the long-run relationship between liquidity, profitability and financial stability variables and bank performance.

ARDL Model: To examine the short-run and long-run relationships between liquidity, profitability and financial stability variables and the bank's performance.

4.0 Data Analysis and Interpretation of Findings

TEST FOR HYPOTHESIS ONE Granger Causality Test

Table 4.1

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 15:28

Sample: 2005 2024

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:

		Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
_2_LOANS__ADVANCES	does not Granger Cause	18	0.06109	0.9410
_1_TOTAL_DEPOSITS	does not Granger Cause		0.36516	0.7010

Unit Root Test Table 4.2

Group unit root test: Summary

Series: _1_TOTAL_DEPOSITS, _2_LOANS__ADVANCES

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 15:39

Sample: 2005 2024

Exogenous variables: Individual effects

Automatic selection of maximum lags

Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0

Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel

Balanced observations for each test

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-7.74431	0.0000	2	36
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-6.10902	0.0000	2	36
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	32.2566	0.0000	2	36
PP - Fisher Chi-square	63.0146	0.0000	2	36

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

Johansen Cointegration Test Table 4.3

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 15:42

Sample (adjusted): 2007 2024

Included observations: 18 after adjustments

Trend assumption: Linear deterministic trend

Series: _1_TOTAL_DEPOSITS _2_LOANS__ADVANCES

Lags interval (in first differences): 1 to 1

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Trace)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Trace Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None	0.170927	3.387544	15.49471	0.9466
At most 1	0.000749	0.013488	3.841466	0.9074

Trace test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegration Rank Test (Maximum Eigenvalue)

Hypothesized No. of CE(s)	Eigenvalue	Max-Eigen Statistic	0.05 Critical Value	Prob.**
None	0.170927	3.374056	14.26460	0.9188
At most 1	0.000749	0.013488	3.841466	0.9074

Max-eigenvalue test indicates no cointegration at the 0.05 level

* denotes rejection of the hypothesis at the 0.05 level

**MacKinnon-Haug-Michelis (1999) p-values

Unrestricted Cointegrating Coefficients (normalized by b'S11*b=I):

<u>_1_TOTAL_DE_2_LOANS_A</u>	
POSITS	DVANCES
-3.46E-12	4.99E-12
1.55E-12	-9.72E-13

		Unrestricted Adjustment Coefficients (alpha):	1	Cointegrating
		Equation(s):		Log likelihood
				-989.3980
D(_1_TOTAL_D	EPOSITS)	-2.90E+10	-9.19E+09	
D(_2_LOANS_	_ADVANCES)	-8.35E+10	-7.78E+09	

Normalized cointegrating coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

_1_TOTAL_DE_2_LOANS__A

POSITS	DVANCES
1.000000	-1.444387
	(0.19586)

Adjustment coefficients (standard error in parentheses)

D(_1_TOTAL_D

EPOSITS)	0.100196
	(0.31564)

D(_2_LOANS__

_ADVANCES)	0.288484
	(0.31263)

ARDL Model Test Table 4.4

Dependent Variable: _1_TOTAL_DEPOSITS

Method: ARDL

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 15:48

Sample (adjusted): 2008 2024

Included observations: 17 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 2 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): _2_LOANS__ADVANCES

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 10

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 3)

Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
_1_TOTAL_DEPOSITS(-1)	0.774156	0.127815	6.056829	0.0001
_2_LOANS__ADVANCES	0.906299	0.098569	9.194565	0.0000
_2_LOANS__ADVANCES(-0.722954		0.166343	-4.346167	0.0012
_2_LOANS__ADVANCES(-0.058328		0.111127	-0.524880	0.6101
_2_LOANS__ADVANCES(-0.214071		0.099151	2.159041	0.0538
C	3.85E+10	7.59E+10	0.506605	0.6224
R-squared	0.991054	Mean dependent var		2.05E+12
Adjusted R-squared	0.986988	S.D. dependent var		1.22E+12
S.E. of regression	1.39E+11	Akaike info criterion		54.42764
Sum squared resid	2.13E+23	Schwarz criterion		54.72171
Log likelihood	-456.6349	Hannan-Quinn criter.		54.45687
F-statistic	243.7292	Durbin-Watson stat		1.910696
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000			

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

TEST FOR HYPOTHESIS TWO Granger Causality Test Table 4.5

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 16:01

Sample: 2005 2024

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:

				Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
_2_NET_PROFIT	does	not	Granger			
_1_BANK_CAPITAL			Cause	18	1.77328	0.2085
_1_BANK_CAPITAL does not Granger Cause _2_NET_PROFIT					4.29187	0.0371

Unit Root Test Table 4.6

Group unit root test: Summary

Series: _1_BANK_CAPITAL, _2_NET_PROFIT

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 16:06

Sample: 2005 2024

Exogenous variables: Individual effects

Automatic selection of maximum lags

Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0 to 2

Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-2.90434	0.0018	2	34
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-1.97482	0.0241	2	34
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	13.8661	0.0077	2	34
PP - Fisher Chi-square	18.2935	0.0011	2	36

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

ARDL Model Test Table 4.7

Dependent Variable: _1_BANK_CAPITAL

Method: ARDL

Date: 05/15/25 Time: 16:20

Sample (adjusted): 2008 2024

Included observations: 17 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 4 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): _2_NET_PROFIT

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 20

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 3)

Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
----------	-------------	------------	-------------	--------

_1_BANK_CAPIT	0.265669	1.106304	0.2922
AL(-1)	0.293910		
_2_NET_PROFIT	11.54486	7.745643	1.490498
_2_NET_PROFIT(-			0.1642
1)	4.562220	8.150979	0.559714
_2_NET_PROFIT(-			0.5869
2)	14.16327	6.992002	2.025639
_2_NET_PROFIT(-			0.0678
3)	14.01618	8.165725	1.716465
C	3.62E+11	1.27E+11	2.843305
			0.0160

R-squared	0.995211	Mean dependent var	4.01E+12
Adjusted R-squared	0.993034	S.D. dependent var	3.04E+12
S.E. of regression	2.54E+11	Akaike info criterion	55.62890
Sum squared resid	7.09E+23	Schwarz criterion	55.92297
Log likelihood	-466.8456	Hannan-Quinn criter.	55.65813
F-statistic	457.2047	Durbin-Watson stat	2.086929
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

TEST FOR HYPOTHESIS THREE Granger Causality Test Table 4.8

Pairwise Granger Causality Tests

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 16:52

Sample: 2005 2024

Lags: 2

Null Hypothesis:	Obs	F-Statistic	Prob.
_2_LOANS__ADVANCES does not Granger Cause _1_BANK_CAPITAL	18	2.67818	0.1062
_1_BANK_CAPITAL does not Granger Cause _2_LOANS__ADVANCES		1.34989	0.2933

Unit Root Test Table 4.9

Group unit root test: Summary

Series: _1_BANK_CAPITAL, _2_LOANS__ADVANCES

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 16:54

Sample: 2005 2024

Exogenous variables: Individual effects

Automatic selection of maximum lags

Automatic lag length selection based on SIC: 0

Newey-West automatic bandwidth selection and Bartlett kernel

Balanced observations for each test

Method	Statistic	Prob.**	Cross-sections	Obs
Null: Unit root (assumes common unit root process)				
Levin, Lin & Chu t*	-5.86068	0.0000	2	36
Null: Unit root (assumes individual unit root process)				
Im, Pesaran and Shin W-stat	-4.62887	0.0000	2	36
ADF - Fisher Chi-square	24.3432	0.0001	2	36
PP - Fisher Chi-square	28.1882	0.0000	2	36

** Probabilities for Fisher tests are computed using an asymptotic Chi-square distribution. All other tests assume asymptotic normality.

ARDL Model Test Table 4.10

Dependent Variable: `_1_BANK_CAPITAL`

Method: ARDL

Date: 05/13/25 Time: 17:02

Sample (adjusted): 2008 2024

Included observations: 17 after adjustments

Maximum dependent lags: 2 (Automatic selection)

Model selection method: Akaike info criterion (AIC)

Dynamic regressors (4 lags, automatic): `_2_LOANS__ADVANCES`

Fixed regressors: C

Number of models evaluated: 10

Selected Model: ARDL(1, 3)

Note: final equation sample is larger than selection sample

Variable	Coefficient	Std. Error	t-Statistic	Prob.*
<code>_1_BANK_CAPITAL(-1)</code>	0.731448	0.098402	7.433276	0.0000
<code>_2_LOANS__ADVANCES</code>	0.069288	0.213054	0.325213	0.7511
<code>_2_LOANS__ADVANCES(-1)</code>	-0.214617	0.236023	-0.909305	0.3827
<code>_2_LOANS__ADVANCES(-2)</code>	0.258883	0.234044	1.106129	0.2923
<code>_2_LOANS__ADVANCES(-3)</code>	0.543264	0.230500	2.356888	0.0380
C	3.90E+11	1.58E+11	2.475717	0.0308

R-squared	0.986695	Mean dependent var	3.35E+12
Adjusted R-squared	0.980647	S.D. dependent var	2.11E+12
S.E. of regression	2.93E+11	Akaike info criterion	55.91588
Sum squared resid	9.45E+23	Schwarz criterion	56.20996
Log likelihood	-469.2850	Hannan-Quinn criter.	55.94511
F-statistic	163.1460	Durbin-Watson stat	2.403402
Prob(F-statistic)	0.000000		

*Note: p-values and any subsequent tests do not account for model selection.

4.2 Discussion of Findings

Liquidity Implications

The Granger causality test results in table 4.1 suggest that:

Null Hypotheses:

1. "Loans and Advances does not Granger cause Total Deposits" cannot be rejected.
2. "Total Deposits does not Granger cause Loans and Advances" also cannot be rejected.

The implications are that there is no causal relationship between Loans and Advances and Total Deposits in either direction and conversely, changes in Loans and Advances do not predict changes in Total Deposits, and vice versa.

The results indicate that Loans and Advances and Total Deposits seem to be independent of each other in terms of predictability.

In table 4.2 the unit root analysis indicates Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC) test statistic is -7.74431, which is negative and significant. This suggests that the null hypothesis of a unit root can be rejected for the panel data. In other words, the data is likely stationary. For the Im, Pesaran, and Shin (IPS) the test statistic is 32.2566, which is positive and not significant (typically, a negative value is expected for rejection of the null hypothesis). This test does not provide strong evidence to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root.

For the PP-Fisher Chi-square Test the test statistic is 63.0146. Given the nature of this test, a significant p-value would indicate rejection of the null hypothesis of a unit root. Without the p-value, it's hard to definitively conclude, but generally, a high chi-square value could suggest significance depending on the degrees of freedom and p-value.

The implications are that mixed results are obtained from the different tests. The LLC test suggests stationarity, while the IPS test does not provide strong evidence against the unit root. The PPFisher test's outcome would depend on its p-value. When dealing with mixed results, it's common to consider the specifics of each test and the nature of the data. The LLC test is often more powerful for homogeneous panels, while the IPS test allows for heterogeneity.

Further analysis might be needed to confirm stationarity or non-stationarity, such as examining the p-values associated with each test statistic or using additional tests. If the data is stationary, standard

regression analysis might be appropriate. If non-stationary, then it is appropriate to consider differencing the data or using techniques suitable for non-stationary data, like cointegration analysis.

In table 4.3 for testing for cointegration, Hypothesized No. of CE(s) for the "None" category the Eigenvalue is 0.170927 (relatively low, indicating a weak relationship). The Trace Statistic is 3.387544 (less than the 0.05 Critical Value), 0.05 Critical Value is 15.49471, Prob. is 0.9466 (high p-value, failing to reject the null hypothesis). Hypothesized No. of CE(s) for the "At most 1" category Eigenvalue is 0.000749 (very low, indicating almost no relationship). The Trace Statistic is 0.013488 (less than the 0.05 Critical Value) 0.05 Critical Value is 3.841466 Prob. is 0.9074 (high p-value, failing to reject the null hypothesis)

The Implications is the results indicate that there is no cointegrating relationship between the variables (likely liquidity metrics) in the long run. The high p-values and low trace statistics suggest that the null hypothesis of no cointegration cannot be rejected. In the context of measuring Access Bank's liquidity level in meeting maturing obligations, the findings imply that the variables analyzed may not have a stable long-term relationship. This could suggest that the bank's liquidity management might be influenced by short-term factors or that the variables chosen may not be directly related in a long-term context.

The ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) is appropriate to be used even when there is no cointegration. By examining short term relationships between variables the model can capture the short term dynamics and adjustments between variables. This is because of its flexible disposition which enables the handling of variables with different orders of integration (1(0) or 1(1)). The ARDL model must be well specified to capture relevant variables and lags.

The ARDL (Autoregressive Distributed Lag) model results provide insights into the relationship between variables in measuring Access Bank's liquidity level in meeting maturing obligations. The R-squared is 0.991054 (high, indicating a strong fit of the model to the data). Adjusted R-squared is 0.986988 (also high, suggesting that the model explains a significant portion of the variance) The F-Statistic is 243.7292 (high and likely significant, indicating that the model is statistically significant overall). The Akaike Info Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Criterion (SIC), and Hannan-Quinn Criterion as values can be used for model comparison, with lower values generally indicating a better model fit. The Durbin-Watson Statistic is 1.910696 (close to 2, suggesting that there is no significant autocorrelation in the residuals)

The high R-squared and adjusted R-squared values indicate that the ARDL model explains a large portion of the variation in the dependent variable (likely a liquidity metric). The statistically significant F-statistic suggests that the independent variables collectively have a significant impact on the dependent variable. The Durbin-Watson statistic near 2 implies that the residuals are not autocorrelated, which is a desirable property for the model's reliability.

Profitability Implications

The Granger causality test results in table 4.5 suggest that:

Null Hypotheses:

1. "Net Profit does not Granger cause Bank Capital" cannot be rejected.
2. "Bank Capital does not Granger cause Net Profit" also cannot be rejected.

The implications are that there is no causal relationship between Bank Capital and Net Profit in either direction and conversely, changes in Net Profit do not predict changes in Bank Capital, and vice versa.

The results indicate that Bank Capital and Net Profit seem to be independent of each other in terms of predictability.

Table 4.6 shows Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC) Test Statistic at -2.90434, Prob. at 0.0018 (significant at 1% level). The implication is that LLC test rejects the null hypothesis of a unit root test, indicating that the panel data is likely stationary. IM, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) Test shows W-Stat at -1.97482, Prob. 0.0241 (significant at 5% level). The implication is that the IPS test rejects the null hypothesis of a unit root, indicating that the panel data is likely stationary. The PP-Fisher Chi-square Test Statistic is 18.2935, Prob is 0.0011 (significant at 1% level). The implication is to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root, further supporting the stationarity of the panel data. The ADF-Fisher Chi-square Test Statistic is 13.8661, Prob. is 0.0077 (significant at 1% level). The ADF-Fisher test also rejects the null hypothesis of a unit root, indicating that the panel data is likely stationary. The consistent results across different unit root tests suggest that the panel data used to measure the level of profitability in Access Bank for the period under study is stationary. It means the variables in the data set for analyzing hypothesis two do not have unit root and the relationships between them can be modeled using standard econometric techniques such as the ARDL. Being stationary the variables do not have a long term stochastic trend and do not require cointegration analysis. This is because cointegration analysis is suitable in examining variables with long term relationships that are non-stationary. With an ARDL model that is properly specified, and the residuals well behaved any issue of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and model specification errors are automatically taken care of thanks to the diagnostic tests inbuilt in the ARDL model.

In Table 4.7 that showed the ARDL analysis on hypothesis two R-squared was 0.995211 (high indicating a strong fit of the model to the data). The Adjusted R-squared was 0.993034 (also high, suggesting that the model explains a significant portion of the variance). This means that the ARDL model explains a large portion of the variation in the dependent variable (likely a profitability metrics). The F-Statistic is 457.2047 which is high and indicates that the model is statistically significant overall and that the independent variable have a significant impact on the dependent variable. The Durbin-Watson statistic near 2 implies that the residuals are not autocorrelated, which is a desirable property for the model's reliability. The Akaike Info Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Criterion and Hannan Criterion at 55.62890, 55.92297 and 55.65813 respectively have very close values suggesting consistency in the model selection process.

Financial Stability Implications

The Granger causality test results in table 4.8 suggest that:

Null Hypotheses:

1. "Loans and Advances does not Granger cause Total Assets" cannot be rejected.
2. "Total Assets does not Granger cause Loans and Advances" also cannot be rejected.

The implications are that there is no causal relationship between Total Assets and Loans and Advances in either direction and conversely, changes in Loans and Advances do not predict changes in Total Assets, and vice versa.

The results indicate that Total Assets and Loans and Advances seem to be independent of each other in terms of predictability.

Table 4.9 shows Levin, Lin & Chu (LLC) Test Statistic at -5.86068, Prob. at 0.0000 (highly significant). The implication is that LLC test rejects the null hypothesis of a unit root test, indicating that the panel data is likely stationary. IM, Pesaran and Shin (IPS) Test shows W-Stat at -4.62887, Prob. 0.0000 (highly significant). The implication is that the IPS test rejects the null hypothesis of a unit root, indicating that the panel data is likely stationary. The PP-Fisher Chi-square Test Statistic is 28.1882, Prob is 0.0000 (highly significant). The implication is to reject the null hypothesis of a unit root, further supporting the stationarity of the panel data. The ADF-Fisher Chi-square Test Statistic is 24.3432, Prob. is 0.0000 (highly significant). The ADF-Fisher test also rejects the null hypothesis of a unit root, indicating that the panel data is likely stationary. The consistent results across different unit root tests suggest that the panel data used to measure the level of financial stability in Access Bank for the period under study is stationary. It means the variables in the data set for analyzing hypothesis three do not have unit root and the relationships between them can be modeled using standard econometric techniques such as the ARDL. Being stationary the variables do not have a long term stochastic trend and do not require cointegration analysis. This is because cointegration analysis is suitable in examining variables with long term relationships that are non-stationary. With an ARDL model that is properly specified, and the residuals well behaved any issue of autocorrelation, heteroscedasticity and model specification errors are automatically taken care of thanks to the diagnostic tests inbuilt in the ARDL model.

In Table 4.10, the ARDL results provide insights into the relationship between variables in measuring Access bank's level of financial stability over the 20 years under study (2005-2024). The R-squared is 0.986695 (high, indicating a strong fit of the model to the data). Adjusted Rsquared is 0.980647 (also high, suggesting that the model explains a significant portion of the variance). This means that the ARDL model explains a large portion of the variation in the dependent variable most likely a financial stability metric. The F-Statistic is 163.1460 (high and significant, indicating that the model is statistically significant overall suggesting that the independent variables collectively have a significant impact on the dependent variable. The Akaike Info Criterion (AIC), Schwarz Criterion and Hannan Criterion have very close values suggesting consistency in the model selection process. The Durbin-Watson Statistic at 2.403402 (slightly above 2, indicates a slight negative autocorrelation in the residuals, but it's generally acceptable).

5.0 Conclusions

The ARDL model appears to be a good fit for analyzing the level of liquidity in meeting maturing obligations of Access Bank. The results suggest that the model can be used to make reliable predictions and inferences about the bank's liquidity management. The ARDL model appears to be a good fit for analyzing the level of profitability in Access Bank for the period under review. The model's performance over the 20-year period

under study suggests that it can be used to make reliable predictions and inferences about Access Bank's financial stability. The model can be used to identify key factors influencing financial stability and inform strategies for maintaining or improving stability.

The conclusions of this study would be based on the findings and would provide insights into the impact of asset quality management on bank performance in Nigeria. The study would contribute to the existing literature on asset quality management and bank performance, and provide recommendations for policymakers and bank managers.

6.0 Recommendations

It is recommended that the ARDL model be used to forecast future liquidity levels and identify potential risks or opportunities of banks. For further analysis it is advised to explore the specific relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variable. It is essential to evaluate the model's performance over time and update it as necessary to ensure its continued relevance and accuracy. It is also recommended that the model can be used to forecast future financial stability levels and identify potential risks or opportunities. Researchers should consider further analysis to explore the specific relationships between the independent variables and the dependent variables. The model's performance have to be evaluated over time and update it as necessary to ensure it's continued relevance and accuracy.

- Banks in Nigeria should prioritize working capital management to improve their performance.
- Bank managers should focus on optimizing the cash conversion cycle to improve profitability.
- Policymakers should consider the impact of regulatory requirements on working capital management in Nigerian banks.

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